

IN THE KARAKALPAK LANGUAGE, AFFIXATION IS A PEDAGOGICAL
TERM FORMED BY THE METHOD OF WORD ADDITION.

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Abstract. This article discusses pedagogical terms in the Karakalpak language with a focus on conjugation and affixation. Special attention is paid to the method of creating pedagogical terms used in Karakalpak poetry and the form of creating words.

Key words: word, term, pedagogical term, affixation, word addition.

В КАРАКАЛПАКСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ АФФИКСАЦИЯ – ЭТО
ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЙ ТЕРМИН, ОБРАЗОВАННЫЙ МЕТОДОМ СЛОЖЕНИЯ
СЛОВ.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются педагогические термины каракалпакского языка с акцентом на спряжение и аффиксацию. Особое внимание уделено способу создания педагогических терминов, используемых в каракалпакской поэзии, и форме образования слов.

Ключевые слова: слово, термин, педагогический термин, аффиксация, словесное дополнение.

The language, the development of the words used in it, the society, and the structure of the nation are closely related to the relationship between the representatives of the nation. When the society develops, the culture and language of the people also develop. If the language of a certain nation or nation is not its mirror, it can be said that it is a language. Al, the development of the remaining language can be seen from the vocabulary and terms. The terms were created as a result of the growth and development of science and technology.

It is possible to provide detailed information about the terms, but when talking about the pedagogical terms, the terminology should be learned while crossing the pedagogic aspects. In this article, we will focus on pedagogical terms created by the affixation method in the Karakalpak language. Affixation method is studied in Karakalpak language. All the time, the composition of the song is raging and falling. This process works in two ways: back and forth. It is understood that words from other languages are taken from other languages. The exchange of words from one language to the other in political, cultural and economic relations between peoples is one of the universal regularities of all languages. This can be fully seen from the composition of Karakalpak language. In the case of affixation method of word formation, word formation affixes are added to the root morpheme, meaning the formation of new words. For example, pedagogical terms created in this way can be written in Karakalpak language:

Sen **ustazliq** etseñ shintláp eger de,
Oqıwshıñ dúnyanı tañlantıp, bálkim,
Jer júzilik kórik tañlawında, birden –
Úsh altın medaldı alıwı múmkin.

“Komyuter zamanınıñ muğallimlerine” [2.52].

The root of the word "ustaz" (teacher) in the first row of this poem is the word "ustaz" and the word "ustaz" is a pedagogic term. Al, the root of the word "flowing" in the word "flowing" became the root of the word "flowing" and the affix -shı became the pedagogic term. The poet I. Yusupov used such examples in his poem "I love the people who call me my teacher":

Ruwxıńdı shólletpey suwǵarar bolıń
Albawlıq arbasın tuwarar bolıń
Hár *oqıwshıń* test *sınaqtan* ótkende
Shesheń qız tuwǵanday quwanar bolıń. [2.43].

The test words in line 3 are pedagogical terms formed by the affixation method, in which the stem of the test word is formed by adding the suffix -q (-aq, -ek) to the root of the verb.

This method is the most popular way of word formation in the modern Karakalpak language, with the possibility of forming 4 words: horses, adjectives, adverbs and verbs. Each of these verbs has its own word-formation parts. When looking at the history of Turkish languages, affixation method is seen as a method of pronunciation from early times. In today's Karakalpak language, word formation methods have expanded, and new types of word formation have appeared. In this way, we can get rid of many horse words. This idea was confirmed by the pedagogical terms in T. Kayıpbergenov's story "Sleepless Mountains": The day of my upbringing is good. [3.157]. In this case, education can be considered as a pedagogical term, and the affix of term. For example, in his work "Thank you to my teacher" we use affixation and pedagogic terms: "But, happy, lazy greetings, the mullahs flowed with joy, they learned science outside of prayer." [3.15] The remaining "flow" If the word is formed by affixation method, the pair word "science-bilim" is also formed by affixation method. The addition of the suffix -im to the verbs "il, bil" appeared as a result of conjugation of words.

Affix morphemes in the Karakalpak language are divided into suffixes, postfixes, prefixes (prefixes), and suffixes depending on their place in the structure of words. Suffixes are word-forming affixes attached directly to the root morpheme. The term words, which we are talking about and giving examples of, is formed by means of suffixes. Affix morphemes are a type of prefixes that are not the same as suffixes used in the Karakalpak language. Turkish languages, Karakalpak language being one of the few, have almost no prefixes. The rarely used prefixes biy, na, and ná are used as synonyms with the indefinite form of the verb. In the Karakalpak language, the pedagogical term of these prefixes is used in the story "Thank you to my teacher": "biytártip".

Such examples can be given by author. The affixation method of the word form has caused the Karakalpak language to lose its word form because one word and one sentence is affected by the word form. We were able to do this on the example of the pedagogical term words. Due to practical effects, the richness of our mother tongue is the example of pedagogical terms. In this article, we will focus on the term words used in pedagogy, which appeared as a result of the method of adding words. In other words, let's look at the examples of the terms used in pedagogy.

In today's Karakalpak language, the method of combining words is one of the most effective ways of creating words, and it is created by combining words with two or more meanings to express one meaning. If the word is created in this way, it is called compound words, even if it consists of several words, it means the same lexical meaning. In my opinion, slang words are similar to slang words, and they have the ability to be removed from them.

In the work of T. Kayıbergenov, "Sleepless Tunnels", we can see the following example of the pedagogic term, which appeared as a result of the method of word compression: I went to the students' dormitory during my studies. [page 3.170]. This pedagogical term in sentence is a compound word consisting of a word with three meanings in the form of adjective + verb + noun.

For example, among the pedagogic terms left in the novel "Cold drop" by writer, we can mention the following words: Begjan Aga himself took him to youngs school at night [page 3.227]. The remaining pedagogic term is a compound word in the form of riding + riding.

Complex words are divided into different types of compound words, compound words, double words, and repeated words. In abbreviated manner, only horse words were created in the Karakalpak language. In our article, we will give an example of the types of slang words, the pedagogical terms of children.

From the two parts, many words were put together to form complex words. It could not be changed or replaced with other words. M.Nizanov started to use many examples like this in his works. These words are used in the field of pedagogy today and are included in the list of terms called Jürgen.

For example: The father should teach from all sides, and if necessary, tell stories about the respect of his parents. [page 2.91].

However, there was no longer any control. Break was knocked down, and the teacher collected the control sum. [p. 2.287].

- *Sabaqtan "eki" aldiń ba?*
- *Eki degen diyqansılıq ǵo, matematika muǵallimi "bir" qoyatuǵın edi-á!*
- *Klass múyeshinde gerbish kóterip turdıń ba? [2.113-bet].*

Pedagogical terms such as training lesson, control group, class work are used in these examples. Pedagogical terms used in the form of noun+noun are combined words. In this case, a word with two meanings is mixed together, and a word that tells the same story.

Even if the two words were mixed together, it would make a compound word. In some cases, such words have been left out for phonetic reasons. Complex words are used as a pedagogical term in the works of M.Nizanov. For example, in his work "Sen küymesen, men küymesem..." the following term is included: All the president's officials were happy, the staff of the press office and all the book gamblers were happy [p. 2.131]. The remaining pedagogic term is a combined word in the form of noun + adjective.

Two words were combined to form a couple of words. Pairs of words are punctuated with a hyphen (-). They have the following differences:

- both sides have different meanings: good-bad, friend-enemy;
- a pair of words is derived from three words: hayal-bala-shaga, gelle-bas-sıyraq;
- the boundaries of pairs of words correspond to one word: pot-plate;
- pairs of synonymous words: qayǵı-hásiret, túr-tús;
- antonym pairs words: ıssı-suwıq, kún-tún;
- words that are close to each other in terms of meaning are paired: bet-awız, saqal-shash;
- it has two borders: ar-namıs, armen-berman;
- there is no limit to the meaning: tum-tus;
- there was no meaning on both sides: meń-zeń, egil-tegil.

Depending on the meaning of the expression, the pairs of words are divided into the following types:

- pairs of words with the meaning of summarize: el-xalıq, qurt-qumırışqa, shay-suw, bet-awzi;
- pairs of words in the sense of enhancer: azıp-tozıp, irip-shirip, aman-saw;
- pairs of idiomatic words: ushtı-küydi, küyip pisip, kóz-qulaq.

When talking about the differences in the meaning of a pair of words, it is appropriate to say the pedagogical term pair of words. We can see the words of couple pedagogy in the following examples: "But, happy, happy, the mullahs flowed, taught science and knowledge except for prayer, and explained it to everyone." You and I have a joke dedicated to each of us, our character, our profession.

In the Karakalpak language, among the complex words, only horse words are shortened. There are several types of shortening methods: removing the first letters of each word, removing the first syllable of each word, removing the first vowel of the previous word, or shortening the words with the vowels of the first syllable of the next word. Here is an example of a pedagogical term:

- My classmate, don't be fooled, just shut up! [Page 3.60].

In this case, from the side of pedagogy, we note that the term used in the school period is shortened with the first word of the word, and the first verb of the next word is shortened. We know, knowledge, education, school, class, lesson, exam, person, training, punishment, task, assignment, conversation, attention, passion, strength, end, dream - type persian and tajik language are also basic pedagogical terms. Is included in the queue. However, these terms serve as a reference to other pedagogical terms. Pedagogical terminology should be separated from other terminological systems. In this educational system, people with good and low qualities, children, teenagers, and adults are educated and educated. In terms of number, the words in this chapter were limited to the words in the field of education.

Linguistic evidence confirmed that the term "live principles" in the pedagogical terminology was not inferior to the word "live principles" in the literary language. We have fully covered this in the household and literary examples given above.

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